

Synthesis of 1-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets and their antimicrobial activity

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1-Tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (4) have been prepared by the interaction of 1-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide (2) with aryl isothiocyanates (3), and screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Recently, we have reported several tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl thiocarbamides (1)¹. Now we report the synthesis of some 1-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets along with their antibacterial and antifungal studies.

The reaction of 1-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide (2) (prepared by interaction of tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-*H*-thiocarbamide and benzyl chloride) and phenyl isothiocyanate (3a) afforded 1-tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-5-phenyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (4a).

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|-----------------------|----------------------------|
| a R = Phenyl | d R = <i>p</i> -Tolyl |
| b R = <i>o</i> -Tolyl | e R = <i>o</i> -Cl. Phenyl |
| c R = <i>m</i> -Tolyl | f R = <i>m</i> -Cl. Phenyl |

Bz = COC₆H₅

Scheme 1

The compounds were screened for their antibacterial activities against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *P. vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus* sp. and *Salmonella* sp. by cup-plate method² at a concentration 100 μ g ml⁻¹ in DMF using the standard cotrimazine (25 μ g ml⁻¹). Compounds 4b, e and f showed higher and others showed moderate activity.

The compounds were also screened for their antifungal activities by cup-plate method at concentration 100 μ g ml⁻¹ in DMF using the standard griseofulvin (10 μ g ml⁻¹) against *A. niger* and *Fusarium* sp. Compounds 4e and f

showed significant activity against *Fusarium* while other compounds were resistant against *A. niger*.

Experimental

The aryl isothiocyanate was prepared by the reported method³. Compound 1 was prepared by the interaction of ammonia and tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate. The required tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate was prepared by the reported method¹.

1-Tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide (2): A mixture of tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-*H*-thiocarbamide (1: 0.01 mol, 6.5 g), benzyl chloride (0.01 mol, 1.2 g) and ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 90 min. The resulting acidic solution when rendered basic with dil. NH₄OH yielded a granular solid (6 g), which was crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 166° (Found : N, 3.69; S, 4.24. C₄₂H₃₆O₉N₂S calcd. for : N, 3.76; S, 4.30%).

1-Tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-5-phenyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (4a): Phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol, 1.3 g) was added to a benzene solution of 2 (0.01 mol, 7.4 g in 30 ml) and the mixture was refluxed over a boiling water-bath for 3 h. Then benzene was distilled off and the resulting syrup triturated several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) followed by ethanol to afford a solid (73%) which was crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 177° (Found : N, 4.67; S, 7.30. C₄₉H₄₁O₉N₃S₂ calcd. for : N, 4.77; S, 7.28%); [α]_D²⁵ -86.20° (c, 0.464; CHCl₃); ν_{\max} 3357 (NH), 1591 (C=N), 1097 (C=S), 1728 (C=O), 854 cm⁻¹ (β -D-glucopyranosyl ring deformation)⁺⁶; δ (TMS; CDCl₃) 8.0 (NH), 7.3–7.4 (ArH), 4.2–4.6, 5.1–5.9 (m, pyranosyl ring)⁶; *m/z* 879 (14), 787 (16), 744 (90), 578 (30), 391 (40), 307 (35), 289 (30), 154 (100), 136 (70), 105 (98).

Other compounds (4b-f) of the series were prepared (yields 50–80%) similarly : 4b, m.p. 144°; [α]_D²⁵ -66.96 (c

Note

0.448; CHCl_3); **c**, 118d, -38.16 (*c* 0.524); **d**, 122°, -68.96 (*c* 0.580); **e**, 64d, -189.87 (*c* 0.316); **f**, 88d, -83.89 (*c* 0.596).

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